

APPLICATION OF EPS GEOFOAM AS A BACKFILL MATERIAL IN BOTH STATIC AND DYNAMIC LOADING CONDITIONS FROM THE PERSPECTIVE OF BANGLADESH

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Abstract

Expanded Polystyrene (EPS) geofoam acts like a compressible buffer between the backfill soil and the retaining wall. It absorbs a large portion of both static and dynamic stresses induced by the backfill soil and transfers the remainder to the retaining structure. Geofoam between retaining wall and backfill soil has the ability to control the development of deformation, that is caused by those uncertain loads. As Bangladesh is prone to earthquakes, geofoam was required to construct a durable structure as a compressible material behind the retaining wall. In this study, the influence of installing geofoam as a compressible buffer behind the diaphragm retaining wall on the soil of Chittagong against static and dynamic loads was studied using Plaxis2D software to create a finite element model. The numerical study took into account the density of EPS, the relative thickness of EPS, and the excavation of single-storied (3m) and multi-storied (3m & 6m) basements with piled-raft foundations. It was found from the numerical analysis that increasing the thickness of EPS geofoam reduced the displacement of the retaining wall by 28.30% to 46.45% in the single-basement and 30.09% to 49.65% in multi-basement compared to no geofoam condition. Furthermore, it was discovered that reducing the density of EPS geofoam in the single-basement and the higher density in the multi-basement reduced lateral displacement by a significant margin.

Keywords

EPS geofoam; Density; Excavation; Finite element analysis; Seismic loading.

1. Introduction

The retaining walls are used in the soil to support the soil laterally and to restrain soil to a slope. There are several types of retaining walls like gravity walls, cantilevered walls, diaphragm walls, anchored walls, and sheet & bored pile walls, etc. In this study, the diaphragm wall had been used to evaluate the results. Diaphragm walls reintegrate a site with construction potential. These walls are the practical solution for underground structures in congested urban areas [1]. After excavation and insertion of the diaphragm wall, it experiences both static and dynamic lateral loads. As a result, the wall sometimes can't withstand these erratic loads. So, Expanded Polystyrene (EPS) geofoam is necessary to use as a compressible buffer between the diaphragm wall and the backfill soil, which can absorb a huge amount of load and pass the remainder to the retaining structure. It is a polymeric foam and is structured with tangentially fused beads. The formation of the closed cells is in an arrangement of a tridimensional structure. The expansion of beads throughout the production process creates these cells [2].

Three types of EPS were tested under seismic loading behind a retaining wall. An elasticized EPS geofoam of 14kg/m³, a type I (16kg/m³) EPS geofoam, and a 57% cored EPS geofoam of Type XI (12kg/m³ – after coring 6kg/m³) were used for the shaking table test. The curve of time and displacement stated that with decreasing density, both the vertical

and horizontal load of the seismic thrust induced by the shaking table reduced significantly. The hysteric response curve showed that with time the horizontal peak force decreased with EPS geofoam of lower elastic modulus [3].

The stress-strain correlations of EPS varied considerably with density. A study of micro and macro mechanical behavior of EPS with the density of 17 - 30 kg/m³ with the confining stress of 0, 30, & 60 KPa showed that initial elastic modulus, plastic modulus, and yield stress increased with the density under compression, Poisson's ratio decreased. As a result, the initial elastic modulus, plasticity modulus, and yield stress also increased [4].

Khan and Meguid numerically modeled and experimented with four types of EPS with densities of 15, 22, 29 & 39 kg/m³ under dynamic loading. The outcome of the numerical analysis displayed that for given backfill soil with an internal friction angle of 40° and EPS thickness ratio to the wall height of 0.3, the peak seismic force on the wall amplified about 17%, with the increase of density from 15 - 39 Kg/m³. Softer geofoam absorbed more energy [5].

The vertical stress exposure of EPS and Poisson's ratio contrasted the lateral and longitudinal strains it encountered. When the stress-strain behavior is linear, it increases linearly with the density of the block, but it decreases fast for larger strains [6]

EPS geofoam of thickness ratios 0.05, 0.1 & 0.2 to wall height were numerically modeled with expanding soil. Here granular backfill was also used as a backfill material behind the retaining wall for comparison purposes with EPS. The outcome of the test exhibited that EPS geofoam worked much more effectively than the granular backfill soil and with increasing the thickness of EPS geofoam the lateral earth pressure reduced significantly [7].

Different thickness ratios of EPS to wall height from 0.1 to 0.3 were investigated numerically in three different tests. The seismic peak force on the wall was lowered by 26% with raising the EPS thickness ratio from 0.1 to 0.3 for a specified backfill with an internal friction angle of 40° and EPS density of 15Kg/m³. As a result, thicker geofoam can compress more and absorb more energy [5]. A numerical parametric study of EPS19, EPS22 & EPS29 with a buffer thickness ratio of 0.025, 0.05, 0.1, 0.2 & 0.4 to wall height was conducted against dynamic loading induced by a shaking table. The excitation frequency ratio of 0.3, 0.5, 0.85, 1.2 & 1.4 to the fundamental frequency was determined to excite the system. For a wall height of 6m with EPS19 and excitation frequency of 30% of the fundamental frequency, the total forces on the wall reduced by 23% with a buffer thickness of 0.3m, and this reduction increased to almost 40% when the geofoam thickness was raised to 1.2m [8].

EPS geofoam was used in increasing the sustainability of a supporting wall situated in an increasing traffic roadway embankment. The cushion foundation was installed between the wall and the backfill soil. The opposite side of the EPS construction is stepped down below the slope of the adjacent soil, resulting in significantly reduced earth pressure applying to the wall [9].

The ability of EPS geofoam barriers to reduce ground wave vibration was explored. The discoveries showed that low-impedance materials, such as EPS geofoam, are particularly good at reducing wave amplitude [10].

EPS geofoam had been used in many countries in the practical situation from the beginning of its arrival. In 1972, the Norwegian Public Roads Authority (NPRA) first utilized geofoam to reconstruct the Flom Bridge embankment [11]. In 2001, The Utah Department of Transportation employed EPS geofoam as a lightweight fill material in the restoration of Interstate I-15 in Salt Lake City, USA [12].

Bangladesh is a very vulnerable country with a high risk of earthquake attacks. Chittagong, Dhaka, Sylhet, Mymensingh, Rajshahi, Rangpur, Comilla, Bogra are extremely vulnerable to severe earthquakes. During the last 150 years, seven major earthquakes (Magnitude ≥ 7) attacked Bangladesh. Earthquake damages like ground rupture, soil liquefaction, landslides, and many other damages to soils affect buildings, roads, and different structures severely. Depending upon the earthquake intensity in different areas, Bangladesh has been divided into three main earthquake zones [13]. In this study, the collected soil of Chittagong of earthquake zone-2 was evaluated against the earthquake effect on the retaining wall with EPS geofoam. The study was constructed against static and dynamic loading conditions. The aim of this study is, by conducting numerical analysis to determine the impact of geofoam on retaining walls, to analyze the influence of geofoam density and thickness on the deformation of retaining walls, to analyze the effect of varying backfill soil properties with EPS geofoam and to evaluate the effect of excavation depth with EPS geofoam.

2. Data Collection

The soil of Chittagong was collected, as the town had seen a significant increase in tall building construction in recent years. Geological characteristics, retaining structures, construction techniques, and craftsmanship all impacted deep excavations in Chittagong soil. Finite element analysis was a powerful technique for investigating excavation behavior.

2.1. Field Test

As a field test, the Standard Penetration Test (SPT) was carried out. In the event of the Chittagong site, the wash boring approach was employed to obtain a disturbed sample with SPT N value computed every 1.5m for 30m. The test process follows ASTM D 1586. (ASTM 1989).

2.2. Laboratory Test

A tri-axial test was performed as a laboratory test to determine the strength and stress-strain relationship. A cylindrical specimen of an undisturbed sample was used to perform the test. The test was carried out until the specimen failed or showed 20% axial strain. According to ASTM D4767 04, the tri-axial test was performed.

3. Material

3.1. Backfill Soil of Chittagong

The research region, according to the site investigation report, is largely made up of coastal deposits. At the time of drilling, the groundwater table was revealed to be 0.9m below the ground surface, which changes depending on the season. The soil profile is separated into three sublayers based on variances in soil qualities, as well as physical and mechanical properties. A 10.5m layer of soft clay and a 9.5m layer of thick silty fine sand comprise the subsoil. Underneath the silty fine sand is a 10.5m thick layer of hard silty clay.

Table 1: Input parameters for Mohr-Coulomb model of Chittagong soil

Parameters	Unit	Formation		
		Stiff Silt Clay	Medium Dense Fine Sand	Very Dense Silty Fine Sand
Unit Weight, γ_{unsat}	kN/m ³	17	20	17
Dry Unit Weight, γ_{sat}	kN/m ³	16	17	15
Cohesion, C'	kPa	5	0	1
Angle of Friction, ϕ	Degree	30	34	18
Dilation Angle, Ψ	Degree	0	4	0
Modulus of Elasticity, E	kPa	27500	31000	31000
Poisson's ratio, ν		0.3	0.3	0.3
Shear Modulus, G	kN/m ²	10577	11924	11924
Interface factor, R_{int}		0.7	0.7	0.7

3.2. Geof foam

The polymeric foam was structured with tangentially fused beads. The cellular structure of this compressible material is filled with 95% air of the total volume. The pre-expansion and molding process is needed respectively to manufacture EPS. 80°C to 110°C temperature is needed for the pre-expansion process. After the expansion by the heat, the molding process starts, and finally, an EPS is constructed [14]. An EPS under uniaxial compression was observed at different strains percentage. At 20% & 39% strains the EPS was fully in a plastic state and at 60% it started the densification process. But after unloading the micro EPS structure recovered 50% of its deformation [4]. EPS geof foam behaved more like linear elastic material [15].

EPS15, EPS22 & EPS29 were used to evaluate the effectiveness of reduction of lateral loads on the diaphragm wall. The considered thickness ratios of EPS were 0.1 & 0.2 to wall height.

Table 2: Input parameters of EPS geofoam

Parameters	EPS15	EPS22	EPS29
Material model	Linear Elastic	Linear Elastic	Linear Elastic
Unit weight (KN/m ³)	0.15	0.22	0.29
Young's Modulus (KN/m ²)	4,200	6,910	10,000
Poisson's ratio	0.11	0.12	0.13

3.3. Structural Elements

The diaphragm wall, strut, raft, and embedded pile, these structural elements were used for the numerical modeling. Both positive and negative interfaces were implemented during modeling.

Table 3: Input parameters of structural elements

Parameters	Unit	Diaphragm Wall	Raft Foundation	Strut
Material Type		Elastic	Elastic	Elastic
Axial Stiffness	kN/m	$7.5 * 10^6$	$5 * 10^6$	$2 * 10^6$
Bending Stiffness	kNm ² /m	$1 * 10^6$	8500	-
Poisson's Ratio		0	0	-

Table 4: Input parameters of the embedded pile

Parameters	Unit	Embedded Pile
Unit weight	kN/m ³	24
Modulus of Elasticity	kN/m ²	$30 * 10^6$
Diameter	M	0.5
Material Type	-	Elastic

4. Modeling using PLAXIS 2D

In this study, several two-dimensional finite element models have been analyzed by using PLAXIS 2D. The plain strain was selected as the finite element model. It is suitable for geometries with uniform cross-sections. Also, the plain strain model is best suited for earthquake simulation which is done by applying load at the bottom of the structure. 15 node triangular elements were selected. It provides high-quality test results due to fourth-order interpolation and involves 12 gauss/ stress points.

The soil behavior is modeled as the Mohr-Coulomb model. It is a well-known model that is based on Hook's law of isotropic elasticity and an extended variant of Coulomb's failure criteria. According to the Mohr-Coulomb model soil behaves linearly. Undrained A is used as the drainage mode for all soil levels.

As EPS geofoam acted more like linear elastic material, so the considered three types of geofoams were modeled as linear elastic material.

The diaphragm wall was modeled as a plate element along with a raft. Strut was represented as a beam element, and pile as an embedded beam element. Mesh was generated setting the element distribution to medium.

Figure 1: Numerical model of single-storied basement with pile raft foundation with geofoam

Figure 2: Generated mesh of double storied basements with pile raft foundation with geofoam

Figure 3: Numerical model of double storied basements with pile raft foundation with geofoam

Figure 4: Generated mesh of double storied basements with pile raft foundation with geofoam

4.1. Excavation Sequence Modeling

PLAXIS2D divided finite element calculation into several sequential calculation points known as “Phases”. Each of the phases represented a type of loading or construction stage. The phases of the numerical model used in this paper were based on actual construction sequences to perform numerical analysis. Table 5 & Table 6 outline the phases used in the model for pile raft foundation -

Table 5: Summary of phases and their activity for Single Basement

Single Basement		
Phase	Activity	
	Without Geofoam	With Geofoam
1	Install diaphragm wall	Install diaphragm wall
2	-2m soil excavation	Geofoam insertion
3	Install strut at -1m	-2m soil excavation
4	-3m soil excavation	Install strut at -1m
5	Install bored pile	-3m soil excavation
6	Cast base slab	Install bored pile
7	Activate 288kn/m/m load applied on foundation	Cast base slab
8	Simulate earthquake	Activate 288kn/m/m load applied on foundation
9		Simulate earthquake

Table 6: Summary of phases and their activity for Double Basement

Double Basement		
Phase	Activity	
	Without Geofoam	With Geofoam
1	Install diaphragm wall	Install diaphragm wall
2	-2m soil excavation	Geofoam insertion
3	Install strut at -1m	-2m soil excavation
4	-5m soil excavation	Install strut at -1m
5	Install strut at -4m	-5m soil excavation
6	-6m soil excavation	Install strut at -4m
7	Install bore pile	-6m soil excavation
8	Cast base slab	Install bore pile
9	Activate 288kn/m/m load applied on foundation	Cast base slab
10	Simulate earthquake	Activate 288kn/m/m load applied on foundation
11		Simulate earthquake

5. Results and Discussion

A diaphragm wall is a reinforced concrete wall used in deep excavation and also works as a permanent foundation wall. Deformation due to constant earth pressure is a major parameter used to determine the performance of the diaphragm wall. During an earthquake, the earth's pressure increases significantly affecting the stability of the retaining wall. The depth of insertion of the diaphragm wall is 2 times the excavation depth. As a result, for a single-storied basement, the diaphragm wall used was 6m, whereas for a double-storied basement it was 12m.

Three different densities of geofoam with two different thickness ratio to wall height on the retaining structure both on static and dynamic loading is discussed here. Finally, a comparative study will be done to determine which type of geofoam is best suited for different conditions.

Figure 1: Dynamic analysis for a 2 storied basement using Chittagong soil with 0.1 thickness ratio

Figure 2: Dynamic analysis for a 2 storied basement using Chittagong soil with 0.2 thickness ratio

Figure 3: Dynamic analysis for a 2 storied basement using Chittagong soil with 0.1 thickness

Figure 4: Dynamic analysis for a 2 storied basement using Chittagong soil with 0.2 thickness ratio

Figure 5: Dynamic analysis for a single-storied basement using Chittagong soil

5.1. Effect of Density and Thickness of Geofoam

From Fig 1 & 2, for 2 storied basements, it can be seen that for 3 different densities of geofoam there is a very slight difference in reducing the earth pressure acting on the diaphragm wall. Observing Fig. 1, it is apparent that, without geofoam total displacement U_x is 269mm but with geofoam of thickness ratio of 0.1 is 223mm. Whereas if a

thickness ratio of 0.2 is used, from Fig. 2 the total displacement U_x noticeably reduces down to 181mm which is a significant reduction. It is evident that EPS geofoam with higher thickness performs better in reducing deformation.

It is clear from Fig. 1 & 2 that different types of geofoam density have very few effects in reducing the total displacement U_x . But if Graphs 3 & 4 are observed, where total displacement (both x & y-axis) is considered instead of total displacement U_x there is a difference in reducing deformation. From Fig. 3, it can be seen that without geofoam maximum total displacement is 585mm. But for EPS15, EPS22, and EPS29, it reduces down to 427, 416 and 409mm accordingly. It is also observed from the graphs that maximum deformation happens on the ground surface level.

5.2. Effect of Excavation Depth

Fig. 6 clearly indicates that for a 2 storied basement the use of a higher density of geofoam results in a higher reduction in total displacement U . Fig. 7 shows the effect of EPS15, EPS22 & EPS29 using 0.1 & 0.2 thickness ratios when utilized for a single-storied basement. As total displacement U (Graphs 3 & 4) shows a better difference than total displacement U_x , the data was collected in total displacement U .

Observing Fig. 5, it is clear that for a single-storied basement the effect of EPS geofoam is opposite of Fig. 3 & 4. Here geofoam with lower density is able to reduce the effect of earth pressure during earthquakes. Without geofoam total displacement U is 633mm. But for EPS15 total displacement U at 0.1 and 0.2 thickness ratio is 454mm and 339mm accordingly. EPS22 and EPS29 don't perform well at a 0.2 thickness ratio and increase deformation at a 0.1 thickness ratio.

5.3. Effect of Static Loading

Although the earth pressure acting on any retaining structure is higher during an earthquake, it occurs occasionally. Therefore, this section discussed the effect of geofoam in reducing earth pressure during static loading.

Observing Fig. 6 & 7, it can be stated that the use of geofoam plays a role in reducing the effect of static loading. But unlike dynamic analysis, it is very small and sometimes geofoam contributes in increasing the deformation. From Fig. 6, it can be seen that the total displacement U (without geofoam) is 34mm and the inclusion of geofoam reduces it to around 24-26mm. Similar can be said for Fig. 7, where the reduction is around 8-10 mm.

Figure 6: Static analysis for a 2 storied basement using Chittagong soil

Figure 7: Static analysis for a single-storied basement using Chittagong soil

6. Conclusion

In the previous sections, the background of the research, methodology, numerical modeling, and results after numerical analysis were discussed in detail. This section is a brief and synthesized summary:

- Finite element analysis is a computerized method using mathematical equations to determine and predict real-world behavior. Soil modeling, retaining structure modeling, geofoam modeling, and construction sequence modeling were discussed in the finite element analysis procedure.

- Thickness ratio plays a vital role in reducing the effect of earth pressure. For 2 storied basements, using EPS29 with thickness ratio 0.2 results in 28% more reduction of total displacement U compared to that achieved with thickness ratio 0.1 and a reduction of 49.64% compared to without geof foam. And for a single-storied basement, using EPS15 with a thickness ratio of 0.2 results in a 25.33% reduction of total displacement U compared to that achieved with a thickness ratio of 0.1 and a reduction of 46.45% compared to without geof foam.
- Density of geof foam also has an impact on reducing displacement. For 2 storied basements, using EPS thickness ratio 0.2 with EPS29 results in a 6.79% reduction of total displacement U compared to that achieved with EPS15 and a reduction of 49.64% compared to without geof foam. For a single-storied basement, using an EPS thickness ratio of 0.2 with EPS15 results in a 39.46% reduction of total displacement U compared to that achieved with EPS29 and a reduction of 46.45% compared to without geof foam.
- Retaining structure depth also plays an important role on the performance of geof foam. From the previous points, it is seen that for a double basement, a higher density of geof foam results in a higher reduction than the lower density of geof foam. But in the case of a single-storied basement, the lower density geof foam performs significantly better. On the other hand, for both single-storied and double-storied basements, the higher thickness ratio of EPS absorbs more energy than the lower thickness ratio.

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